

THE ROLE OF MUFRAD'S WORK IN IMPROVING HUMAN BEHAVIOR

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Abstract.

This article deals with the ethics selected in connection with the invaluable scientific heritage of Imam Bukhari. It contains information about the work "Al-Adab al-Mufrad" and scientific sources related to the improvement of human behavior, a number of hadiths and messages not found in the works of other authors. There are also quotes and information about "Family", "Educational relations between family members", "Loyalty to the Motherland", "The importance of scientific heritage of ancestors in human development".

Keywords.

Education, heritage, human perfection, family, manners, spiritual refreshment, culture, kindness, hadith, Islamic value.

The Islamic values promoted by Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband, Burhoniddin Marginani and many other scholars are a reflection of our spiritual life and religion. The entire Muslim world recognized that our ancestors who lived and worked in our country raised Islam to a high level of culture and civilization. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his historic speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly: "I would like to note the invaluable contribution of many prominent figures of the Central Asian Renaissance to Islam and world civilization. One such great scholar, Imam Bukhari, is recognized worldwide as the author of "Sahih Bukhari", which is considered the most sacred book after the Holy Quran in the Islamic religion.

In order to preserve and study the rich heritage of this great man, and spread his teachings about enlightened Islam, we decided to establish an international research center named after Imam Bukhari in the city of Samarkand [8: 2].

Also, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018: "Al-Jami' al-Sahih" by the Great Imam

Bukhari, "Actions depend on intentions. There is certainly a very deep meaning in the beginning of the hadith saying, "Whatever one intends will happen to everyone" [10]. Today, it is one of the most urgent problems for our youth to follow the example of the hadiths of the great hadith scholar Imam Bukhari.

When we talk about the unique contribution of our great thinkers and scholars to the development of Islamic culture, first of all, we respectfully mention the blessed names of our grandfather, Imam Bukhari, who has rightly gained great fame in the Muslim world as the "Sultan of Muhaddiths". "Al-Jami' al-Sahih, the collection of reliable hadiths, which is the culmination of the legacy of this honorable man, is the second holy source in the Islamic religion after the Holy Qur'an, and according to the belief of the people of Islam, it is considered the greatest of all books written by mankind." This book illuminates the hearts of millions of people with the light of faith and calls them to the path of truth and religion" [4: 38]. From this point of view, looking at the religious, moral and legal teachings of Imam Bukhari from a new perspective is extremely relevant and has practical significance in a certain sense.

The hadiths of Imam Bukhari teach human qualities such as kindness, generosity, respect for parents and elders, kindness to orphans, love for the Motherland, hard work, honesty, friendly and peaceful coexistence of different peoples, which have great educational value for the whole generation. expressed. The unique legacy collected by our grandfather, Imam Bukhari - authentic hadiths of our Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) is leading all mankind to the path of guidance. The life and scientific activity of the great scholar has been continuously studied in the whole world since time immemorial, and many scientific and popular works have been created about him in the West and the East. One of them is the book "Hayatul Bukhari" ("The Life of Bukhari") by the Syrian scientist Sheikh Muhammad Jamaluddin Qasimi Damascus, which contains a lot of valuable information about the scholar's exemplary life and high scientific potential.

Imam Ismail al-Bukhari's hadiths, who is recognized as the emir of hadith science in science, are more and more mastered by young people. There is no doubt that the hadiths of Imam Bukhari will be a program for our young people who are devoted to the development and prospects of their motherland, and perfect generation [6: 123].

"Al-Adab al-Mufrad" contains a number of hadiths and reports that are not found in the works of other authors. According to some of the critics, the hadiths in "Al-Adab al-Mufrad" are closer in terms of reliability to the hadiths in the author's

"Al-Jami' al-Sahih" and are considered higher than the hadiths in "Alti Kitab" [3: 86].

Here are some examples from the hadiths of Imam Bukhari: The feeling of fatherhood is a manifestation of faith in a person's heart. It is easy to have a child, but not everyone can be a real father and spiritual leader.

Giving birth to a child is only one aspect of the duty of fatherhood and manhood. His main task is to raise his child well and ensure that he takes his rightful place in society.

It is not the father's admonitions for the children, but also the actions, walking and standing...

Another important duty of a father is to raise his children with love. In life, the girl is the support of the father, and the father is the support of the girl.

According to the hadith, "he who raises three daughters, brings them to adulthood and sends them to a suitable place, his reward is paradise." A father's justice, attitude, love, and compassion towards his spouse are of great importance for his children's education. Children learn what justice is from the father's attitude towards the mother.

It is also of great educational value for a man to help his wife in many tasks, to be generous and generous in spending for the family. A man who is the head of the family thinks about the needs and concerns of the family, his trust and respect towards his spouse leaves a deep mark on the spirituality of his children. From this, children try to respect their father more.

The foundation of the family is the parents. Mutual love, trust, cooperation and mutual understanding between parents, respect, sincerity of relations - this is the basis for ensuring family stability - it is a model school for the child.

As Abdurauf Fitrat, a great representative of Turkestan modernism of the 20th century, said: "The husband and wife should be together in the journey of life, which consists of difficulties, share physical and mental peace, assist in fulfilling human tasks, care for each other in times of sadness and despair, and sympathize with each other in times of happiness and joy. Therefore, it is necessary for them, first of all, to examine each other with perfect attention and experience" [7: 23].

Peace and mutual love of parents depends on their worldview, spiritual level, interest, faith, material equality, position in society, good fortune, inclination of their hearts. Children brought up by a couple who match each other with these characteristics will grow up to be passionate about beauty, mentally fresh, wholehearted, curious about life, ready to live a peaceful family life. Otherwise, there will be unkindness between parents and children, dissatisfaction with their

own life and society, unrest in the family, lack of interest in anything, carelessness, indifference, and jealousy. This is the basis for the crisis of the family. Children born and brought up in such an unhealthy environment have a strong tendency to betrayal, various immoral behaviors (drinking, smoking, stealing, crime, drug addiction, etc.) and mental stress. Therefore, compatibility of husband and wife is important in ensuring family stability [6:123].

As the great thinker Alisher Navoi said: "When a husband and a wife match each other, there will be wealth and harmony between them." From it is the decoration of the house and from it is the peace of the married. If there is good, it is pleasing to the heart, if there is good, it is good. If he is smart, his life will be disciplined and his household will be organized and organized. ... A broken couple is a bitter and hideous disease for the home. If he is shameless, his heart will suffer from him, if he is naughty, his soul will suffer from him. If the tongue is bad, the heart of the groom will be hurt. If there is a bad deed, blackness will come to the earth. If it is good, the prosperity of the house will be lost, and if it is bad, the house will become ugly" [2: 201].

In Islam, a man is given great responsibilities to lead the family and therefore the husband is given the appropriate powers.

A true Muslim cannot not follow the values of Islam. Even when entering the house, he should first greet his wife and children and wish them well. "...Whenever you enter houses, say to each other the blessed and pure greeting from God (that is, say "Peace be upon you")" (Surah Noor 24: 61).

Family is sacred. Building a family is a very responsible job. Bringing the young generation to life, creating a certain starting point - starting position for them is different in different nations. In the mentality of some peoples, when children become adults, they leave their families and parents and leave their homes to stand on their own. When he builds a family, has a child and raises it, he also puts an end to the succession of generations and leaves his family [10: 23].

The establishment of a great state in any society depends on how young people are and how they are educated. The well-known pedagogue Abdulla Awlani wrote that "Education is a matter of life or death for us, salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster" [12: 14].

In conclusion, it should be said that raising the young generation in the family based on the example of parents, family traditions, genealogy, profession, moral and spiritual values, and preparing them for family life by forming loyalty to the family, mutual love, and respect in their minds will give the expected result. For this purpose, in order to prepare parents for the process of education, it is

appropriate to restore and improve the work of parents' universities, to include the course "Preparation of young people for family life" in the content of general education schools, higher and secondary special education. Introduction of the "Family Psychology and Pedagogy" course to higher and secondary special educational institutions of all directions through the booklets of the family library series and the special "Family" magazine, which methodically helps parents and family education, is a means of turning the family into an exemplary place of education. It is also important to explain to students the hadiths of Imam Bukhari, which are included in the golden fund, during information and coaching hours.

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